

SYNTHESIS AND PHOTOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF NEW
DIPHENYLACRYLONITRILE-BEARING ALDEHYDESSÍNTESE E PROPRIEDADES FOTOFÍSICAS DE NOVOS ALDEÍDOS CONTENDO
DIFENILACRILONITRILA

التخليق و الخصائص الفيزيائية الضوئية للألدهيدات الجديدة الحاملة لثنائي فينيل أكريلونيتريل

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Received 19 November 2023; received in revised form 08 February 2024; accepted 14 November 2024

RESUMO

Introdução: Através de uma simples condensação aldólica ciano e controlando a temperatura, dois aldeídos contendo difenilacrilonitrila foram sintetizados, e suas estruturas foram confirmadas por técnicas de infravermelho, ^1H , ^{13}C -RMN e massa. Suas propriedades fotofísicas também foram estudadas em diferentes solventes orgânicos polares e não polares (clorofórmio, THF e DMSO). Os máximos de absorção dos compostos variam entre (300-400 nm), enquanto os espectros de emissão variam entre (400-500 nm) com deslocamento de Stokes vermelho entre 68-86 nm. A adição de água em suas soluções de THF ligeiramente melhorou sua característica de emissão induzida por agregação (AIE). **Objetivos:** Síntese de unidades de acrilonitrila via condensação aldólica ciano, controle de temperatura e estudo da atividade AIE. **Métodos:** A síntese de unidades de acrilonitrila de difenil ocorreu em duas etapas: 1- Por meio da o-arilação, aldeídos lineares foram sintetizados, 2- Adicionando gradualmente cianeto de p-ansiyl aos aldeídos lineares em um balão redondo contendo metanol e KOH. **Resultados:** Unidades de acrilonitrila de difenil foram sintetizadas, e suas estruturas foram verificadas usando IR, $^1\text{HNMR}$, $^{13}\text{CNMR}$ e técnicas de massa. Os resultados fotofísicos forneceram dados indicando que os compostos de aldeídos contendo difenilacrilonitrila possuem fluorescência com um comprimento de onda variando entre 400-500 nm e atividade AIE moderada. **Discussões:** As unidades de aldeídos contendo difenilacrilonitrila preparadas mostraram atividade AIE moderada no estado de agregação, onde a intensidade de fluorescência aumenta com o aumento da porcentagem de água na mistura THF/H₂O e atinge o pico em 80%. A razão reside no fato de que o grupo ciano forma acrilonitrila com estruturas torcidas, o que evita ACQ e aprimora as propriedades AIE. **Conclusões:** controlando a temperatura e através de uma condensação aldólica fácil, unidades de fenilacrilonitrila foram sintetizadas em bons rendimentos. Suas propriedades fotofísicas foram estudadas, e constatou-se que possuem atividade AIE moderada.

Palavras-chave: *Difenilacrilonitrila, rendimentos quânticos, emissão induzida por agregação (AIE), deslocamento de Stokes.*

ABSTRACT

Background: The cyano group is well-known for its strong electron-withdrawing properties, Effective in producing acrylonitrile when added to π -conjugated alkene structures. The twisted structures of acrylonitrile help avoid the ACQ phenomenon and induce AIE properties, making acrylonitrile units important in various applications. **Aims:** Synthesis of acrylonitrile units via cyano aldol condensation by temperature control and study of AIE activity. **Methods:** The synthesis of diphenyl acrylonitrile units took place in two steps: 1- By o-arylation, linear aldehydes were synthesized, 2- Gradually adding p-ansiyl cyanide to the linear aldehydes in a round flask containing methanol and KOH. **Results:** Diphenyl acrylonitrile units were synthesized, and their structures were identified using IR, $^1\text{HNMR}$, $^{13}\text{CNMR}$, and mass techniques. The photophysical results indicated

that diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehyde compounds have fluorescence with a wavelength ranging between 400-500 nm and moderate AIE activity. **Discussion:** The prepared diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes units showed moderate AIE activity in the aggregation state, where the fluorescence intensity increases with increasing water percentage in the THF/H₂O mixture and reaches its peak at 80%. The reason lies in the fact that the cyano group forms acrylonitrile with twisted structures, which avoids ACQ and enhances the AIE properties. **Conclusions:** by controlling the temperature and through a facile aldol condensation, phenylacrylonitrile units were synthesized in good yields. Their photophysical properties were studied, and they were found to have moderate AIE activity.

Keywords: Diphenylacrylonitrile, quantum yields, aggregation-induced emission (AIE), Stokes shift.

المخلص

الخلفية: تعتبر مجموعة السيانو من افضل المجاميع الساحبة للإلكترون ، وهي فعالة بشكل خاص في إنتاج الأكريلونيتريل عندما تُضاف إلى هياكل الألكين المتعاقبة. تساهم التراكيب الملتوية للأكريلونيتريل في تجنب ظاهرة تخميد التجمع (ACQ) وتحفيز خصائص التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث الخاص بالفلورة الجزيئية (AIE)، مما يجعل وحدات الأكريلونيتريل مهمة في مجموعة متنوعة من التطبيقات. **الأهداف:** تصنيع وحدات الأكريلونيتريل عن طريق تكثيف السيانو الدول، والتحكم في درجة الحرارة، ودراسة فعالية التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث. **طرائق العمل:** تم تصنيع وحدات ثنائي فينيل أكريلونيتريل على خطوتين: 1- بواسطة الأريلية تم تصنيع الأدهيدات الخطية، 2- إضافة *p-ansiyl cyanide* تدريجياً إلى الأدهيدات الخطية في دورق دائري يحتوي على الميثانول وهيدروكسيد البوتاسيوم. **النتائج:** تم تصنيع وحدات ثنائي فينيل أكريلونيتريل، وتم التحقق من بنيتها باستخدام تقنيات الأشعة تحت الحمراء، ¹H، ¹³C-NMR وطيف الكتلة. أعطت النتائج الفيزيائية الضوئية بيانات تشير إلى أن مركبات الأدهيدات الحاملة لثنائي فينيل أكريلونيتريل تمتلك فلورة بطول موجي يتراوح بين 400-500 نانومتر وفعالية معتدلة من التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث. **المناقشة:** أظهرت وحدات الأدهيدات الحاملة لثنائي فينيل أكريلونيتريل نشاط معتدل من التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث، حيث تزداد شدة التألق مع زيادة نسبة الماء في خليط THF/H₂O وتصل إلى ذروتها عند 80%. السبب يكمن في حقيقة أن مجموعة السيانو تجعل الأكريلونيتريل بهياكل ملتوية، مما يتجنب تخميد التجمع ويعزز خصائص التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث. **الاستنتاجات:** من خلال التحكم في درجة الحرارة ومن خلال تكثيف الأدول البسيط، تم تصنيع وحدات الفينيل أكريلونيتريل في عوائد جيدة. تمت دراسة خصائصها الفيزيائية الضوئية، ووجد أن نشاطها معتدل من التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث الخاص بالفلورة الجزيئية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: ثنائي فينيل أكريلونيتريل، عائد الكم، ظاهرة التجمع الناتج عن الانبعاث الخاص بالفلورة الجزيئية (AIE)، تحول ستوكس

1. INTRODUCTION:

The cyano group is considered one of the best electron-withdrawing groups, which, when added to the π -conjugated structures of alkenes, results in acrylonitriles (scheme 1) that have unique alterations in their conformation, stability, packing mode, processability, and solubility (C. Wang *et al.*, 2017; Xing *et al.*, 2016; Zhao *et al.*, 2018).

Further, acrylonitriles are an example of a typical structural pattern commonly found in agrochemicals, pharmaceuticals, herbicides, and natural products (Fleming *et al.*, 1999; Fleming *et al.*, 2010). More importantly, a donor can be introduced to the acrylonitrile skeleton to create fluorescent materials with acceptor and donor-conjugated structures and nonlinear optical characteristics, which are excellent for two-photon excited imaging in live samples due to high spatial resolution, deep tissue penetration, and minimal background fluorescence (Guo *et al.*, 2014; C. Wang *et al.*, 2017). Recently, great efforts have been made to synthesize acrylonitriles with diverse functions and substitutions. (Barrado *et al.*, 2017; Chaitanya *et al.*, 2015; Paquin *et al.*, 2015; X. Wang *et al.*, 2018). Allyl azides were synthesized by reacting allyl halides or esters with NaN₃ or TMSN₃ catalyzed by Pd(PPh₃)₄ and then converting them

to alkenyl nitriles (or acrylonitriles) using DDQ as the oxidant (Scheme 1) (T. Wang *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, for the purpose of developing various acrylonitriles, the direct cyanation route of alkenes has also been adopted (Chaitanya *et al.*, 2015; Gao *et al.*, 2018; Su *et al.*, 2015; X. Wang *et al.*, 2018). Engle *et al.* reported novel oxidative cyanation of terminal and internal alkenes utilizing a homogeneous copper catalyst to obtain acrylonitrile (Gao *et al.*, 2018). Accordingly, many acrylonitriles have been synthesized. Still, these methods require hazardous and toxic agents, harsh reaction conditions, low atomic economy, and expensive transition metal complexes. Direct functionalities of acrylonitriles are still challenging, and this area needs further improvement. Via a transition metal-free, non-toxic, nonhazardous, and atom-economic nucleophilic reaction, research groups discovered that aldehydes or ketones and propane nitriles were reactants for direct production of acrylonitriles using conventional bases such as NaOH, t-BuOK. (Lee *et al.*, 2013; Shi *et al.*, 2016; Wei *et al.*, 2018; Zhu *et al.*, 2012). As a result, this kind of nucleophilic reaction may have enormous promise for the facile and direct synthesis of versatile acrylonitriles with various functionalities.

The aggregation-induced emission (AIE) effect was reported by Tang's group (Hong *et al.*,

2009, 2011; Luo *et al.*, 2001; M. Wang *et al.*, 2010). AIE is a particular photophysical phenomenon in which some luminous gives off weak or no fluorescence in solution, but the emission increases greatly in the aggregated and solid state (Chen *et al.*, 2019; He *et al.*, 2019; Hu *et al.*, 2018; Y. J. Li *et al.*, 2019; Ni *et al.*, 2018). Previous studies have shown that cyano groups make the acrylonitrile with twisted structures, which leads to avoiding aggregation-caused quenching (ACQ) and AIE properties in the aggregate state in aqueous environment (B. K. An *et al.*, 2002; Lim *et al.*, 2004). Many multicolor brightly emissive AIE luminogens (AIEgens) have been synthesized based on acrylonitriles and applied in various fields such as one- and two-photon bioimaging and fluorescence sensing (K. Y. Kim *et al.*, 2018; Mandal *et al.*, 2015; C. Y. Yu *et al.*, 2017). Because of the minimal background autofluorescence, deep tissue penetration, and reduced photodamage, acrylonitriles with bright red emission are particularly preferred in bioimaging (Haque *et al.*, 2017; J. Bin Li *et al.*, 2019; Yuan *et al.*, 2013). Unfortunately, acrylonitrile-based AIEgens with highly red-emissive are still rare (B. An *et al.*, 2009; M. Kim *et al.*, 2015; Lu *et al.*, 2016; Paramasivam *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2014). In addition, their synthesis involves multi-step reaction methods and time-consuming isolation or purification due to their complicated structures (Niu *et al.*, 2019).

This work aims to synthesize different acrylonitriles bearing aldehydes via metal-free, non-toxic, and atom-economic transformation through cyano aldol condensation. The photophysical properties of the prepared acrylonitriles were also evaluated.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Provide sufficient details to permit repetition of the experimental work. A technical description of the methods should be given when they are new.

2.1. Materials

The following materials were used in this study: p-hydroxybenzaldehyde, p-anisyl cyanide, 1,3-dibromopropane, 1,4-dibromobutane, anhydrous sodium carbonate, potassium hydroxide, dichloromethane, chloroform, tetrahydrofuran, dimethyl sulfoxide, N,N-dimethylformamide (laboratory reagent grade),

petroleum ether, ethanol, methanol, and silica gel (100–200 mesh).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1 Method of Synthesis of 4,4'-[alkane-1,2-diylbis(oxy)]dibenzaldehyde (R1 and R2)

At room temperature, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (81.9 mmol), dibromoalkane [(CH₂)_n n = 3, 4] (40.9 mmol), and Na₂CO₃ (163.8 mmol) were added to a two-necked round-bottomed flask containing DMF (50 ml). The mixture was stirred and heated to reflux (140 °C for 6 h). TLC monitored the reaction until the reaction was completed. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and quenched with distilled water, filtered and washed with water, and dried to obtain a crude product. The crude products were recrystallized from ethanol to give an off-white solid 4,4'-[alkane-1,2-diylbis(oxy)]dibenzaldehyde in excellent purity. (Devaraju *et al.*, 2013)

2.2.2 Method of Synthesis diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes (R3 and R4)

A p-anisyl cyanide (0.774 mmol in 5ml of methanol) was added gradually (dropwise) to a two-necked round flask containing (0.704 mmol) of 4,4'-[alkane-1,2-diylbis(oxy)] dibenzaldehyde (R1 and R2), KOH (1.76 mmol), (20 ml) methanol at temperature (50 °C for 30 min). After completing the addition, the mixture was stirred and heated to reflux (for 24 hours). TLC monitored the reaction until the reaction was completed after completion of the reaction. The mixture was filtered, the filtrate was taken and dried by a rotary evaporator, and the product was purified via silica gel column chromatography using (DCM: Petroleum ether; 3:2) as eluent to give the product as a solid in excellent purity. (Q. Yu *et al.*, 2020).

2.2.3 Method for measuring the photophysical properties of diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes(R3 and R4)

Solutions with a concentration of (1×10⁻⁵ M) were prepared, and the absorbance was measured in a number of polar and nonpolar solvents (DMSO, THF, chloroform), and fluorescence was measured at the same concentration. UV-visible spectra were recorded on the Shimadzu UV-spectrophotometer (UV-1800), and Fluorescence spectra were obtained on the Shimadzu spectrofluorophotometer (RF-5301pc). UV-vis and fluorescence spectra were

plotted using the spectrograph program (software for optical spectroscopy, version 1.2.16.1).

2.2.4 Method of studying AIE behavior for diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes (R3 and R4)

The effect of AIE on the THF/H₂O was studied. This was done by preparing a solution of R3 and R4 in proportions from 0 to 80% and measuring the fluorescence at 350 nm (whereas λ_{ex} of diphenylacrylonitrile = 350nm).

2.2.5 Method for calculation of the quantum yields

The fluorescence quantum yields of the compounds R3 and R4 in chloroform, THF, and DMSO were calculated using the relative Method (comparison method). The quantum yields of a sample are calculated by comparing the fluorescence intensity with another sample of known quantum yields as a reference. This requires knowing the absorbance of both the sample and the reference (Tryptophan was used as a reference in the fluorescence spectrum), considering the refractive index of the solvents used (Brouwer, 2011; Suzuki *et al.*, 2009).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Spectroscopic characterization of linear aldehydes (R1 and R2)

3.1.1.1 4,4'-[alkane-1,2-diylbis(oxy)]dibenzaldehyde (R1 and R2) 4,4'-(propane-1,3-diylbis(oxy))dibenzaldehyde (R1):

White crystals. Yielded 51% , m.p.124-125 °C; IR (KBr): 2947 (CH₂), 3070 (CH-Ar) 1693 (C=O), 1600 (C=C), 1111 (C-O) cm⁻¹,¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 9.86 (s, 2H, CHO), 7.86 (s, 4H, Ar-H), 7.15 (s, 4H, Ar-H), 4.26 (s, 4H, OCH₂), 2.24 (s, 2H, CH₂), ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 191.4 (C=O \times 2), 163.5 (Ar-C \times 2), 131.9 (Ar-CH \times 4), 129.7 (Ar-C \times 2), 115.0 (Ar-CH \times 4), 64.8 (OCH₂ \times 2), 28.3 (CH₂).

3.1.1.2. 4,4'-(butane-1,4-diylbis(oxy))dibenzaldehyde (R2):

Golden crystals. Yield 52%, m.p. 98-100 °C; IR (KBr): 2951 (CH₂), 3059 (CH-Ar) 1685 (C=O), 1604 (C=C), 1111 (C-O) cm⁻¹,¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 9.86 (s, 2H, CHO),

7.85 (s, 4H, Ar-H), 7.11 (s, 4H, Ar-H), 4.15 (s, 4H, OCH₂), 1.90 (s, 4H, CH₂), ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 191.3 (C=O \times 2), 163.6 (Ar-C \times 2), 131.9 (Ar-CH \times 4), 129.6 (Ar-C \times 2), 114.9 (Ar-CH \times 4), 67.7 (OCH₂ \times 2), 25.2 (CH₂ \times 2).

3.1.3. Spectroscopic characterization of diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes (R3 and R4)

3.1.3.1. (Z)-3-(4-(3-(4-formylphenoxy) propoxyphenyl)-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)acrylonitrile (R3):

Light green crystals. Yield 47% m.p. 103-105 °C; IR (KBr): 2943-2885 (aliph.C-H), 3032 (Ar. C-H), 1685 (C=O), 1600 (C=C), 1118 (C-O) , 1361 (C-N) cm⁻¹ ;¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 9.86 (s, 1H, CHO), 7.85-7.91 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.81 (s, 1H, C=CH), 7.65 (d, 2H, J= 8.7 Hz, Ar-H), 7.15 (d, 2H, J= 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.11 (d, 2H, J= 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.05 (d, 2H, J= 8.7 Hz, Ar-H), 4.26 (t, 2H, J= 6.0 Hz, OCH₂), 4.22 (t, 2H, J= 6.0 Hz, OCH₂), 3.80 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.24 (quin, 2H, J= 6.0 Hz, CH₂); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 191.3 (C=O), 163.5 (Ar-C), 160.0 (Ar-C), 159.8 (Ar-C), 140.3 (CH=C), 131.9 (Ar-CH \times 2), 130.9 (Ar-CH \times 2), 129.7 (Ar-C), 126.9 (Ar-CH \times 2), 126.6 (Ar-C), 126.5 (Ar-C), 118.5 (CN), 115.0 (Ar-CH \times 2), 114.9 (Ar-CH \times 2), 114.6 (Ar-CH \times 2), 106.9 (C), 64.8 (OCH₂), 64.4 (OCH₂), 55.4 (CH₃), 28.4 (CH₂); HRMS (ESI+) m/z: (M+Na⁺) calcd C₂₆H₂₃NNaO₄⁺ 436.1525, found 436.1524.

3.1.3.2. (Z)-3-(4-(4-(4-formylphenoxy)butoxy) phenyl)-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)acrylonitrile (R4):

White crystals. Yield 45% , m.p. 123-125 °C; IR (KBr): 2943 (aliph.C-H), 3028 (Ar. C-H) 1689 (C=O), 1600 (C=C), 1111 (C-O) cm⁻¹ ,1392 (C-N);¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 9.86 (s, 1H, CHO), 7.85-7.91 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.82 (s, 1H, C=CH), 7.65 (d, 2H, J= 8.7 Hz, Ar-H), 7.04-7.14 (m, 6H, Ar-H), 4.12-4.16 (m, 4H, OCH₂ \times 2), 3.80 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.91 (m, 4H, CH₂ \times 2); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): ppm δ 191.3 (C=O), 163.6 (Ar-C), 160.2 (Ar-C), 159.8 (Ar-C), 140.4 (CH=C), 131.8 (Ar-CH \times 2), 130.8 (Ar-CH \times 2), 129.6 (Ar-C), 126.9 (Ar-CH \times 2), 126.5 (Ar-C), 126.4 (Ar-C), 118.6 (CN), 114.9 (Ar-CH \times 2), 114.8 (Ar-CH \times 2), 114.6 (Ar-CH \times 2), 106.8 (C=CH), 67.7 (OCH₂), 67.4 (OCH₂), 55.4 (CH₃), 25.2 (CH₂ \times 2); HRMS (ESI+) m/z: (M+H⁺) calcd C₂₇H₂₅NO₄⁺ 428.1862, found 428.1857.

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1 Synthesis and characterization

The diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes R3 and R4 were synthesized with good yield in two steps (Scheme 2); (i) by *o*-arylation, linear dialdehydes were synthesized, using the 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde and dibromoalkane $[(\text{CH}_2)_n, n = 3, 4]$ in the presence of anhydrous sodium carbonate in DMF. (ii) The linear dialdehyde R1 and R2 reacted with *p*-anisyl cyanide using the facile nucleophilic reaction in the presence of KOH in MeOH. IR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$, and mass spectra characterized the synthesized compounds.

3.2.1.1. 4,4'-[alkane-1,2-diylbis(oxy)]dibenzaldehyde (R1 and R2)

The IR data of compounds R1 and R2 (Figure 1 and Figure 4), respectively, showed the bond (C=O) of aldehyde group stretching vibration appears in $(1685-1693) \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum further confirmed this in (Figure 2 and Figure 5), respectively. $^1\text{HNMR}$ spectrum of the compounds showed one distinctive singlet at δ (9.86) ppm, confirming the presence of aldehydes protons, as well as the singlet at δ (7.11-7.86) ppm and δ (4.11-4.26) ppm, confirming the presence of aromatic and aliphatic protons, respectively. $^{13}\text{CNMR}$ spectrum of the compounds showed the appearance of a signal for C=O in aldehyde group at δ (191.3-191.4), while the signal of (OCH₂) carbon appears at δ (64.8-67.7) ppm and existence of a peak at δ (25.2-28.3) ppm belong to the presence of (CH₂) group, as shown in (Figure 3 and Figure 6).

3.2.1.2. Diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes (R3 and R4)

The IR spectrum of R3 and R4 compounds showed absorption bands in regions $(2943-2873) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $(3028-3032) \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which belong to aliphatic and aromatic C-H bonds. The bond (C=O) of aldehyde group stretching vibration appears in $(1685-1689) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Figure 7 and Figure 11). $^1\text{HNMR}$ spectrum of these compounds showed singlet at δ (9.86) ppm confirming the presence of aldehyde proton, aromatic protons peaks appear at δ (7.04-7.91) ppm, vinyl proton appears at δ (7.81-7.82) ppm, and protons of (OCH₂) exhibit at δ (4.12-4.4.26) ppm, while signal of (OCH₃) protons appears at δ (3.80) ppm as a singlet, protons of (CH₂) appears

at δ (1.91) ppm (Figure 8 and Figure 12). In the $^{13}\text{CNMR}$ spectrum, signals at δ (191.3) ppm denote the presence of C=O in the aldehyde group, while the signals of aromatic carbons appear at δ (114.6-163.6) ppm. A signal of vinylic CH appears at δ (140.3-140.4) ppm, while the signal of vinylic C appears at δ (106-107) ppm. A signal of OCH₂ carbon appears at δ (67.4 -67.7) ppm, and a signal at δ (55.4) ppm belongs to the (CH₃) group, and the existence of a peak at δ (25.2-28.4) ppm belongs to the presence of CH₂ group (Figure 9 and Figure 13). The mass spectra of R3 and R4, shown in (Figure 10 and Figure 14) respectively, are identical with their calculated mass.

3.2.2 Photophysical properties for diphenylacrylonitrile-bearing aldehydes (R3, R4)

UV-vis absorption and emission spectra were measured in several different organic solvents to obtain an in-depth understanding of the photophysical properties of R3 and R4 (Figure 15, Figure 16, Figure 17, and Figure 18), the absorption spectra of the compounds show absorption peaks belonging to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (300-400 nm) for diphenylacrylonitrile group. It was observed that the two compounds R3 and R4 emit good fluorescence (400-500nm) in all use organic solvents due to the good solubility in these solvents. The effect of solvent polarity on the fluorescence spectra was studied, and it was noted that with increasing solvent polarity, the fluorescence spectra showed a red shift and a corresponding decrease in the fluorescence intensity. For compound R3, the maximum absorption limit in the absorption spectrum (λ_{abs}) ranged between 345-350 nm, while the maximum emission limit in the fluorescence spectrum (λ_{fl}) ranged between 417-434 nm, with a chemical red shift appearing as 72- 86 nm (Table 1). As for compound R4, the maximum absorption limit in the absorption spectrum (λ_{abs}) ranged between 342-350 nm, while the maximum emission limit in the fluorescence spectrum (λ_{fl}) ranged between 416-432 nm, with a chemical red shift appearing as 74-82 nm (Table 1).

To further explore the photophysical properties, mixtures of THF and water with different water fractions were used to investigate the aggregation-induced emission (AIE) behaviors. The fluorescence intensity of compounds R3 and R4 were investigated at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 350 \text{ nm}$ (Figure 19 and Figure 20). It is noted that when the water fraction increases, the fluorescence intensity of these compounds

increases gradually and attains a maximum of 80% because the cyano groups form acrylonitrile with twisted structures, avoiding aggregation-induced quenching (ACQ) and enhancing the AIE properties in the aggregate state in the aqueous environment. This result indicates that the compounds R3 and R4 have moderate AIE features.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion, by controlling the temperature and through a facile aldol condensation, phenylacrylonitrile units were synthesized in good yields 47%, and their structures were confirmed by infrared, ^1H , ^{13}C -NMR, and mass techniques. Their photophysical properties were studied in several polar and nonpolar solvents (DMSO, THF, and chloroform). The effect of solvent polarity on the fluorescence spectra was studied, and it was noted that with increasing solvent polarity, the fluorescence spectra showed a red shift and a corresponding decrease in the fluorescence intensity. The effect of AIE was also studied for both compounds (Z)-3-(4-(3-(4-formylphenoxy)propoxy)phenyl)-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)acrylonitrile (**R3**) and (Z)-3-(4-(4-(4-formylphenoxy)butoxy)phenyl)-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)acrylonitrile (**R4**) it was found that compounds R3 and R4 had moderate AIE activity.

5. DECLARATIONS

5.1. Study Limitations

The study is limited to the sample size and experimental conditions.

5.2. Acknowledgements

The authors want to thank the Chemistry Department for their assistance in completing this study.

5.3. Funding source

The authors funded this research.

5.4. Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

5.5. Open Access

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Scheme 1. Various Strategies to Synthesize Functionalized Acrylonitriles.

Scheme 2. Synthesis Routes to R3, R4

Figure 1. IR Spectrum of the compound R1

Figure 2. ¹H NMR Spectrum of the compound R1

Figure 5. ^1H NMR Spectrum of the compound R2

Figure 6. ^{13}C NMR Spectrum of the compound R2

Figure 7. IR Spectrum of the compound R3

Figure 8. ¹H NMR Spectrum of the compound R3

Figure 9. ^{13}C NMR Spectrum of the compound R3

+MS, 0.7-0.9min #28-34

Figure 10. Mass Spectrum (ESI) of the compound R3

Figure 11. IR Spectrum of the compound R4

Figure 12. ¹H NMR Spectrum of the compound R4

Figure 13. ^{13}C NMR Spectrum of the compound R4

+MS, 0.7-0.9min #27-33

Figure 14. Mass Spectrum (ESI) of the compound R4

Figure 15. The absorption spectra of compound R3 in different solvents (1×10^{-5} M)

Figure 16. The absorption spectra of compound R4 in different solvents (1×10^{-5} M)

Figure 17. The emission spectra of compound R3 in different solvents (1×10^{-5} M) excited at $\lambda = 350$ nm.

Figure 18. The emission spectra of compound R4 in different solvents ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) excited at $\lambda = 350$ nm.

Figure 19. The emission spectra of compound R3 with different fractions of H_2O in THF/ H_2O mixtures ($1 \mu M$) excited at $\lambda = 350$ nm.

Figure 20. The emission spectra of compound R4 with different fractions of H_2O in THF/ H_2O mixtures ($1 \mu M$) excited at $\lambda = 350$ nm.

Table 1. Absorption and fluorescence data of samples R3 and R4 in solvents at 298 K.

Samples.	$\lambda_{\text{abs}}/\text{nm}$	$\epsilon(\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1})$	$\lambda_{\text{em}}/\text{nm}$	Stokes shift/nm	Φ_f	Solvent
Tryptophan	278.5	230000	280	-	0.15	Water
R3	345	150000	417	72	0.021	THF
R4	342	230000	416	74	0.014	
R3	345	140000	431	86	0.021	CHCl ₃
R4	346	160000	425	79	0.02	
R3	350	70000	434	84	0.071	DMSO
R4	350	150000	432	82	0.035	